

DALAM at the 2023 IFLA WLIC

by *Susanna Parikka*, Library Director
Lapland University Consortium Library

The International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) is the global voice for libraries, representing the interests of the profession and working for improving services worldwide. IFLA

holds an annual conference for the whole library and information services sector, the World Library and Information Congress (WLIC), alternating cities and continents. This year the conference was held in Rotterdam, the Netherlands, 21-25 August. It brought together over 3000 participants from 150 countries and all different types of libraries for the 88th time.

My intention was to present Thematic Network DALAM in a poster form to library professionals all over the world. The theme for the conference was "Let's work together, let's library" with the sub-theme of "Building a sustainable future through the SDGs." The work in DALAM is related to the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goal 10, Reduced Inequalities.

The DALAM poster was planned jointly by Sandy Campbell, Shannon Christoffersen, Sharon Farnell, Susanna Parikka, and other members of the DALAM network. It was designed by Shannon Christoffersen.

I think it was important for DALAM to get some global visibility. All the posters will be stored in IFLA's open web archives. During the conference, the attendees were able to view the posters on their own. There were also two special poster sessions when we were able to present our posters. I had some interesting conversations and got new contacts.

Common hot topics in the library world now are literacy, sustainable development, and AI.

The conference program included plenty of fine presentations, some even in the field of decolonization.

The majority of the members voted against the next IFLA WLIC being held in Dubai, United Arab Emirates, but the decision was still made by the lead. This controversial decision led to many discussions, and many library associations said that they will boycott IFLA WLIC 2024. IFLAs' values include democracy and freedom of speech, but these will be threatened in Dubai through censoring of the presentations and posters beforehand. As of 3rd October, according to IFLA's website, the decision has been made to withdraw the invitation to hold the next WLIC in Dubai. There will be no IFLA WLIC next year.

The city of Rotterdam is the largest seaport in Europe, very multicultural, with high buildings and extraordinary architecture, cycle lanes and cyclists everywhere, and lots of water – you could even take a water taxi, a small yellow-black fast motorboat.

Rotterdam. Photos courtesy S. Parikka